

**Navigating change:
the economic impact of the Western
Mediterranean multiannual plan**

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Credits

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Executive summary

The Western Mediterranean Multiannual Plan (West Med MAP), adopted in 2019, was designed to ensure the sustainable exploitation of demersal fish stocks in the western Mediterranean Sea by progressively achieving fishing mortality levels consistent with maximum sustainable yield (MSY) by 2025. Encompassing the Mediterranean waters of France, Italy, and Spain, the plan addresses six key demersal species — blue and red shrimp, deep-water rose shrimp, giant red shrimp, European hake, Norway lobster, and red mullet — while promoting the elimination of discards and the adoption of ecosystem-based management. Despite these ambitious objectives, the plan's implementation has faced significant challenges, and the economic consequences on the trawl fleets of the region appear to be complex and warrant further assessment.

The economic performance of trawl fleets in the western Mediterranean in recent years has been shaped not only by the West Med MAP but also by two major external shocks: the COVID-19 pandemic and energy market volatility triggered by the Russian aggression on Ukraine. These events disrupted supply chains, reduced demand (particularly in the hospitality sector), and dramatically increased operational costs, further straining the economic performance of the fleets.

The analysis of ten distinct trawl segments across France, Italy, and Spain reveals a troubling pattern, observed both before and after the implementation of the West Med MAP, in which **most segments struggle with low or negative profit margins, insufficient return on investment, and declining economic resilience**. Only a few segments — Spanish trawlers under 18 metres length and Italian trawlers between 12 and 18 metres length — have consistently achieved profit margins above the 10% threshold considered necessary for long-term viability. Most others, particularly large French trawlers (over 24 metres) and several Italian segments, have faced a chronic lack of profitability, some for at least a decade, pre-dating the West Med MAP. While public subsidies have provided temporary relief, they have not offset the underlying structural economic challenges.

The imbalance between fishing capacity and available fishing opportunities is a central issue undermining both economic and ecological sustainability. Fleet segments in the western Mediterranean are widely considered to be in a state of overcapacity, with **too many vessels competing for too few fish**. This imbalance is reflected in the biological, technical, and economic indicators used to assess fleet performance. Biological indicators such as the Stock at Risk (SAR) and Sustainable Harvest Indicator (SHI) show that **most segments rely heavily on overfished stocks**, while technical indicators such as the Vessel Utilisation Ratio (VUR) reveal underutilised capacity. Economically, most segments exhibit declining trends in profitability, return on investment, and labour productivity, signalling **a fleet that is both overcapitalised and economically inefficient**.

The West Med MAP has not yet achieved its primary objective of restoring fish stocks to sustainable levels, which is the likely reason why no spillover effect has been observed for less impacted gear types, such as passive gears. Landings of key species like European hake and red mullet have continued to decline across all segments, indicating that the reduction in fishing effort has not yet translated into stock recovery or redistributed fishing opportunities. This underscores the systemic nature of the challenges facing the region's fisheries: **the fleet remains oversized, and the stocks remain overfished, perpetuating a cycle of economic instability and ecological degradation**.

To address these challenges, an integral management approach is required. Short-term efforts should focus on enforcing existing regulations to accelerate stock recovery and reduce overcapacity, while long-term strategies must tackle the structural issues of fleet economic fragility. Public support should be reoriented away from subsidising unprofitable operations and towards facilitating a just socio-ecological transition for fishers and communities. This includes **incentivising gear transitions to more selective and sustainable fishing methods, promoting fleet adjustments through well-designed decommissioning schemes, and assisting fishers and coastal communities through retraining and diversification initiatives**. By aligning public financial support and management measures with sustainability objectives, policymakers can foster a smaller, more resilient and selective fleet that is able to operate profitably on healthy fish stocks.

Ultimately, the future of western Mediterranean fisheries hinges on the ability to restore balance—both ecological and economic. Achieving this will require not only stricter enforcement of conservation measures but also a fundamental rethinking of how the fleet operates within the constraints of a finite resource base. Without decisive action, the region risks continuing down a path of declining profitability, ecological degradation, and missed opportunities for sustainable growth.

1. Introduction

The Western Mediterranean multi-annual plan (West Med MAP)¹ was officially published on 26 June 2019 and entered into force on 16 July of the same year. This regulation serves as a key tool to implement the objectives of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)² in the western Mediterranean Sea. The plan sets out a legally binding five-year transitional framework aimed at progressively achieving, by 1 January 2025, fishing mortality levels consistent with the maximum sustainable yield (MSY)^a for six demersal species (i.e. blue and red shrimp, deep-water rose shrimp, giant red shrimp, European hake, Norway lobster, and red mullet). It further requires these levels to be maintained beyond 2025, the legal deadline to reach target fishing mortality, to ensure that the exploitation of resources restores and maintains populations above MSY levels, securing the long-term sustainability of both the stocks and the fisheries depending on them. The area encompasses the Mediterranean waters of France, Italy, and Spain, including the Alboran Sea, the Gulf of Lion, and the Tyrrhenian Sea, as well as the Balearic archipelago and the islands of Corsica and Sardinia. These areas are defined by the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) as geographical subareas (GSAs);³ the West Med MAP covers GSAs 1 to 11, excluding GSA 4 (Algeria). More broadly, the plan also aims to contribute to the implementation of precautionary and ecosystem-based approaches to fisheries management and the elimination of discards.

Despite the adoption of a wide range of management measures and efforts to implement them, including a reduction of the days at sea for trawlers, seasonal closures, the introduction of catch limits for certain stocks, and increased mesh sizes to improve selectivity, countries have not met the objective of achieving sustainable exploitation of demersal stocks by 2025. Eleven of 13 stocks assessed in the western Mediterranean (85%) remain subject to overfishing, and 77% (10 of 13 stocks) are still below MSY abundance levels, highlighting the need for stronger implementation and enforcement.⁴

While the West Med MAP aims to address overfishing and ensure the long-term sustainability of fish populations in the western Mediterranean, the economic performance of the trawler fleets from France, Italy, and Spain, as well as the impact of the plan on their operations, remains a sensitive topic. Since its adoption in 2019, the fishing vessels covered by the West Med MAP have also been affected by two major external shocks that have shaped their economic outcomes. First, the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted logistic chains and lowered the demand served by these vessels, notably in the HORECA (hotel, restaurant, and catering) sector. Second, the Russian invasion of Ukraine resulted in higher volatility in the energy markets, pushing up energy costs.

Against this backdrop of regulatory ambition and external disruptions, this report seeks to evaluate the economic resilience and adaptability of trawler fleets in France, Italy, and Spain under the West Med MAP. The analysis addresses three core research questions:

1. How have external shocks—such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the energy crisis—combined with MAP-imposed management measures to affect the economic viability of trawling fleets?
2. How have Member States managed fleet capacity in response to these challenges, and what does this reveal about the relationship between fleet size, activity levels, and profitability?
3. What spillover effects, if any, have arisen for fleets using alternative fishing gears, such as longlines and gillnets, as a result of management measures for trawlers under the MAP?

The analysis is based on publicly available data collected by Member States' administrations and aggregated at the EU level, which were complemented by additional data published by Member States (see Section 7).

a. Maximum Sustainable Yield (MSY) is defined in Article 4 of the CFP as “the highest theoretical equilibrium yield that can be continuously taken on average from a stock under existing average environmental conditions without significantly affecting the reproduction process”.

The analysis focused on ten distinct trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean Sea. These segments can be identified in the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) Annual Economic Report (AER)⁵ data (see Section 7.1):

- ➔ **Two in France:** 18-24 m and 24-40 m.
- ➔ **Four in Italy:** 6-12 m, 12-18 m, 18-24 m and 24-40 m.
- ➔ **Four in Spain:** 6-12 m, 12-18 m, 18-24 m and 24-40 m.

The six species covered by the West Med MAP constituted a significant share of the revenues of these ten trawler segments during the period 2016-2019, before the implementation of the West Med MAP (see Figure 1): from just over 20% for French trawlers (both 18-24 m and 24-40 m), to close to 75% for Spanish trawlers above 24 m.⁵

Figure 1. Shares of fishing revenues from the six species covered by the West Med MAP, for trawler segments from the western Mediterranean during 2016-2019.

Source: Data from Prellezo et al. (2024).⁵

2. Profitability analysis

As the West Med MAP seeks to align fishing activities with the principles of MSY, while applying the precautionary and ecosystem-based approaches, understanding the profitability of these fleets is essential for assessing whether the sector can support both ecological recovery and the livelihoods of those who depend on it. Profitability, in this context, is more than just a financial metric; it is an indicator of resilience, adaptability, and long-term survival in an industry facing numerous challenges.

This section examines the profitability of the trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean by addressing four critical questions:

1. How are subsidies distributed to vessel owners?
2. Can vessel owners generate sufficient income to sustain their operations and compete with alternative economic activities?
3. Are they able to replace their aging vessels with new-built boats and invest in the future of their fleets?
4. Are crew members compensated at levels comparable to onshore jobs, ensuring the sector remains attractive to skilled labour?

These questions are not only central to the economic well-being of individual operators but also to the broader sustainability of the fishing industry in the region.

The analysis draws on data from the AER and other sources to evaluate how subsidies, profit margins, return on investment, and crew remuneration interact to shape the economic landscape of the trawler fleets. It also considers the impact of external shocks, such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the energy crisis triggered by the Russian invasion of Ukraine, which have further strained the financial stability of these segments.

» 2.1 Fishery subsidies

Fishery subsidies are financial payments from public entities to the fishing sector, which help the sector generate more profit than it would otherwise.⁶ Public support distributed to fishing vessels falls under two categories: operating subsidies and subsidies on investment. **Operating subsidies** are public financial instruments implemented to help cover ongoing, day-to-day operational costs, while **subsidies on investments** are granted to encourage recipients to acquire, upgrade, or maintain physical assets. Unlike operating subsidies that cover day-to-day expenses, investment subsidies are for one-time, long-lasting purchases. Decommissioning programmes are classed as subsidies on investment.

During the period 2019-2024, the fleet segments from France, Italy, and Spain operating in the western Mediterranean Sea received four types of operating subsidies from their national and regional governments:

- ➔ Two instruments linked to the reduction of fishing effort:
 - The mandatory temporary cessation (MTC) of fishing activities funds to reduce fishing effort, as part of the West Med MAP;
 - The temporary cessation (TC COVID-19) of fishing activities funds to mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak (mainly in 2020 and 2021).
- ➔ Two other instruments that were implemented to cover:
 - The emergency fund (Fund COVID-19) for the fisheries and aquaculture to support companies affected by the COVID-19 outbreak (mainly in 2020 and 2021);
 - The one-off compensation for measures to alleviate the consequences of Russian invasion of Ukraine on fishing activities (Ukraine crisis).

Data on subsidies were obtained from three ad-hoc studies (for Spain⁷, France,⁸ and Italy⁹) that were commissioned by the European Commission to support the STECF expert group on Fishing effort regime for demersal fisheries in West Med (STECF 24-12)¹⁰ (see also Section 7.4). An additional review of public information published by each Member State was conducted to identify missing data (see Table 1). However, data coverage is not comprehensive due to variations in national reporting practices, methodologies, and the timelines for publishing subsidy information.

One of the key issues in understanding how these subsidies may affect profit levels is that **payments are sometimes delayed due to the time required for paperwork processing, verification procedures, and payment warrants**. For example, companies in Italy received the payments covering the 2020 temporary cessation in 2022, in addition to residual payments for 2018 and 2019 temporary cessations.

It is also important to highlight that funds allocated to compensate for the West Med MAP measures represent lower payments than the funds allocated to compensate for the consequences of the Ukraine crisis (i.e. the steep increase in energy prices) for the two countries for which all data are available (i.e. Spain and Italy). Overall, the identified compensation to cover for the effects of COVID-19 (2.7 million euros) and of the Ukraine crisis (9.1 million euros) that have been identified are higher than the support provided to compensate for the effects of the West Med Map (7.5 million euros), bearing in mind that the support for the Ukraine crisis provided by the French administration couldn't be retrieved from public datasets. On the support provided to cover the effects of the West Med Map, most of it has been mostly spent by Italy (5.3 million euros), followed by Spain (1.5 million euros) then France (0.7 million euros).

Table 1. Subsidies (in thousand euros) distributed to the trawler segments of the western Mediterranean, for 2019-2024.

	Instrument	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
France 	MTC			458	1 021		
	TC COVID-19		245				
	Fund COVID-19	No data available					
	Ukraine crisis	No data available					
Spain 	MTC	83	175	205	190	29	
	TC COVID-19		149				
	Fund COVID-19	Instrument not implemented					
	Ukraine crisis				243	3 463	
Italy 	MTC	1 174	1 481	1 301	1 141	243	
	TC COVID-19			71	506	21	
	Fund COVID-19		1 690				
	Ukraine crisis						5 349

Date source: Based on Rodriguez (2024)⁷, Metz (2024)⁸, Sabatella (2024)⁹ and information published by France, Italy, and Spain.

Differences also exist in the way each Member State defines how fishing vessels receive these support packages, the financial tools leveraged, and how the payment calculations are made, with the obligation to publish detailed payments regularly for all the subsidies distributed. To date, not all data have been published under the previous funding framework (the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund, EMFF), on the national pages of the current European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF), in the EU State Aid Transparency database,¹¹ or in records of measures financed through national budgets.

One of the key issues is linked to the tendency to rely on national measures rather than European funds, notably in France, which limits the publication requirements. One way forward would be to make all support provided to fishing vessels should be reported in a central database, no matter which type of instrument is implemented to support the vessels (based on European funds, notified national funds, non-notified national funds).

The figures collected are consistent with the aggregated value of operating subsidies recorded in the AER,⁵ as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Operating subsidies (in thousand euros) recorded in the Annual Economic Report for trawler segments in the western Mediterranean, for the period 2014-2022.

Country	Trawler fleet segment	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
France 	18-24 m	306	373	265	139	84	699	509	224	1 046
	24-40 m	488	575	414	77	65	115	652	475	1 138
Italy 	6-12 m	353	68	0	48	74	46	223	91	114
	12-18 m	5 872	2 282	0	1 676	2 864	884	4 781	2 050	2 045
	18-24 m	5 591	3 003	0	2 160	3 743	1 476	5 805	2 807	2 353
	24-40 m	2 097	1 233	0	1 068	1 201	565	3 023	1 183	1 275
Spain 	6-12 m	0	2	10	0	0	26	0	21	110
	12-18 m	215	45	226	93	85	89	287	436	871
	18-24 m	1 107	1 763	512	461	248	862	1 105	1 627	4 670
	24-40 m	613	122	269	132	241	713	697	627	3 196

Source: Prelezo et al. (2024).⁵

It should be noted, however, that the subsidies data published by Member States are not automatically comparable with AER data because:

1. Member States' data are based on administrative records, while the AER draws from surveys of vessel owners—two distinct and independent processes; and
2. the AER data are the result of several aggregation processes that may blur and misallocate the subsidies as cost reductions.

For example, the French implementation of compensation for the Ukraine crisis consisted in a reduction of social contributions paid by vessel owners. It is unclear whether such support is identified as operating subsidies or if it is aggregated with the crew costs. As a way forward, there is a need for the European Commission and the dedicated STECF working groups to improve their guidance on how subsidies should be considered and reported in

the AER and in all other economic analyses of the fisheries and aquaculture value chains (processing and aquaculture mainly).

» 2.2 Profit margins

The Net Profit Margin measures the percentage of revenue retained as surplus after covering all explicit and implicit costs, including the opportunity costs of labour and capital. It reflects the economic profit and resource rent generated by fisheries, indicating their operating efficiency and capacity to generate surplus compared to alternative uses of labour and capital in the economy.

Net profit margins have been estimated using data published annually in the AER,⁵ under two specific scenarios (i.e. with and without operating subsidies), as

depicted in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Using the thresholds commonly accepted by the STECF working groups on capacity indicators,¹⁶ the trawler segments are labelled:

- ⊙ 'Unprofitable' when profit margins are negative;
- ⊙ 'Not sufficiently profitable' for levels of profit margins between 0% and 10%; and
- ⊙ 'Profitable' when profit margins are higher than 10%.

Figure 2. Net profit margins for trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean, without subsidies. A: Annual figures from 2014 to 2022. B: Comparison of three-year averages before and after the implementation of the West Med MAP.

■ Profitable
 ■ Not sufficiently profitable
 ■ Unprofitable

Source: Prellezo et al. (2024).⁵

Between 2014 and 2022, Spanish trawlers below 18 m (2 segments) and Italian trawlers between 12 and 18 m were the only trawler segments covered by the West Med MAP that regularly presented profit margin levels over 10%, which is considered the threshold for a fishing segment to be sufficiently profitable.

Over the nine-year period, the Italian trawlers between 12 and 18 m only became unprofitable in 2022, and were considered not sufficiently profitable in 2021. The Spanish trawlers between 6 and 12 m were unprofitable in 2019 and 2020 and not sufficiently profitable in 2017 and 2022.

All other trawler segments covered by the West Med MAP were at best not sufficiently profitable and at worst regularly unprofitable. Some segments showed a negative profit margin for several years, notably Italian trawlers longer than 18 m (2 segments), and small Italian trawlers (6-12 m).

Large French trawlers (24-40 m) have been in an extreme situation, systematically showing a negative net profit margin since at least 2014. Despite this unprofitable situation, the segment has remained stable over the period, with no vessel leaving the fleet. This phenomenon has been described in the economic literature, notably by Curtis and Jones (2016) who noted that “for vessels with poor expected performance, [...] owners’ principal concern was “Will I clear my feet?": i.e. would they be clear of debt if they disposed of the vessel?¹² Despite wanting to exit, if they could not rid themselves of debt by scrapping the vessel, owners suggested they might continue to operate unprofitable or low profit boats in anticipation of possible improved fishing opportunities. French vessels benefitted from a permanent cessation support mechanism that was aimed at compensating operators to leave the fishery, but only in 2022 and 2023: its effects will not be captured in the AER data until at least in 2026.

When comparing the average net profit margin over three years before and after the implementation of the West Med MAP (i.e. 2017-2019 compared to 2020-2022), a declining trend could be identified for five segments (all Italian segments and Spain 18-24 m) for which the three-year average net profit margin dropped by more than 5 points (see Figure 2B). One segment (Spain 6-12 m) showed an improvement of its average net profit margin by 7 points. For the other four segments, the variations were too limited to be considered a trend.

Including the operating subsidies reported in the AER in the profit margin calculation did not drastically change the results of the analyses, with profit margin levels that are still considered not sufficiently profitable for most years (see Figure 3). Identifiable subsidies modified the net profit margin ranking only in twelve instances (violet rectangles in Figure 3). Fleet segments that were unprofitable became barely profitable in only six instances: France 18-24 m in 2014, Italy 6-12 m in 2022, Italy 18-24 m in 2014 and 2021, Italy 24-40 m in 2022, and Spain 24-40 m in 2022.

The other six cases consisted of segments that shifted from not sufficiently profitable to profitable, when subsidies were taken into account: France 18-24 m in 2020, Italy 6-12 m in 2014, Italy 12-18 m in 2021, Spain 6-12 m in 2022, Spain 12-18 m in 2019, and Spain 18-24 m in 2017.

It should be noted that there were more unprofitable segments in 2022 due to the energy crisis following the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, which increased fuel prices. A specific support package was deployed in the three countries, but as noted in the previous section, a large share of the Italian vessels only received this specific financial support in 2024, partially explaining why all of them experienced a drop in their net profit margin between 2021 and 2022. Spanish trawlers experienced a similar drop in net profit margin between 2021 and 2022, due to late payment of the Ukraine support package.

Overall, only one trawler segment can be considered unprofitable even with subsidies for the whole 2014-2022 period: French trawlers over 24 m length. Since 2019 and the implementation of the West Med MAP, Italian trawler segments have tended to fall in the same category of being unprofitable even with subsidies: Italian trawlers 6-12 m for three years, Italian trawlers 18-24 m for two years, and Italian trawlers 12-18 m and 24-40 m for one year.

Spanish trawlers 6-12 m were also unprofitable even with subsidies in 2019 and 2020, but these two years seem to be outliers when considering the rest of the period for this segment.

Finally, it should be noted that **including operating subsidies** when comparing the average net profit margin over three years before and after the implementation of the West Med MAP (2017-2019 compared to 2020-2022) **does little to change the declining trend observed in net profit margins** (see Figure 3B). It only changed the status of the Spanish trawlers 18-24 m which was overall not sufficiently profitable during the period 2017-2019 and became profitable thanks to the operating subsidies allocated to these vessels.

Figure 3. Net profit margins for trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean, with subsidies. A: annual figures from 2014 to 2022. B: Comparison of the three-year average before and after the implementation of the West Med MAP. Violet rectangles identify years where subsidies shift the ranking of fleets, in comparison to the scenario without subsidies (see Figure 2).

■ Profitable
 ■ Not sufficiently profitable
 ■ Unprofitable
 Source: Data from Prelezo et al. (2024).⁵

» 2.3 Return on investment

Two indicators were used to understand if vessel owners could finance the renewal of their boats, as depicted in Figure 4. The Return on Investment (ROI) and the Return on Fixed Tangible Assets (ROFTA) indicators compare the long-term profitability of the fishing fleet segment to other available investments. The ROI calculation includes the residual value of the fishing vessels and fishing rights (fishing licences, fishing quotas), while the ROFTA is only based on the residual value of the fishing vessels.

For most segments, the level of return on investment appears to have been sufficient to allow vessel owners to renew their vessels over the period 2014-2022, with a level of return on investment (ROI) that diminished over the period. Two segments were characterised by a more degraded situation: both Italian trawlers under 12 m and

French trawlers above 24 m had negative levels of return on investment over several years.

Figure 4. Return on investment (ROI, at left) and return on fixed tangible assets (ROFTA, at right) for trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean, between 2014 and 2022.

Salz (2025)¹³ recently highlighted that the residual values of the vessels currently active, as recorded in the AER, are potentially too low, especially when compared to the cost of new vessels. If this were proven to be true, it would mean that the actual replacement value of vessels should be set at potentially higher levels for

some segments. These corrections would lower the estimated values for the ROI and ROFTA calculations, thus indicating that more trawler segments were in unprofitable situations.

» 2.4 Crew remuneration compared to national averages

Crew retention and remuneration are among the key elements to understand when assessing the long-term profitability of fishing vessels. The national average wages for full-time equivalents (FTE) for all sectors reported by Eurostat¹⁴ were used to assess whether the remuneration could be considered sufficient for each trawler segment. Results were estimated in terms of percentage difference from the national FTE average (see Figure 5). Positive ratios correspond to situations where crew were paid above the national FTE average, while negative ratios correspond to situations where crew were paid below the national FTE average.

All Italian trawler segments showed a remuneration per FTE that was lower than the Italian FTE average. In Spain, the large trawler segment (above 24 m) was the only segment to offer higher compensation than the

national FTE average between 2016 and 2021. All other Spanish trawler segments were paying the crew at rates below the Spanish FTE average. In comparison, all French trawlers were providing remuneration above the French FTE average.^b

b. The value of 210% for French trawlers between 18 and 24 m length is considered as an outlier.

Figure 5. Comparison between average crew remuneration and the national average FTE remuneration (all sectors), shown as percentage differences by trawling segment, between 2014 and 2022.

Source: Data from Prellezo et al. (2024)⁵ and Eurostat¹⁴ (see Section 7.1).

» 2.5 Overall profitability of the trawler segments

Comparing the profitability status that can be derived from the information on subsidies, profit margins, return on investment, and crew remuneration presented in the previous sections allows to identify fleets that are overall profitable, sufficiently profitable and unprofitable (see Table 3). Three groups of segments emerged:

- ➔ **Profitable segments:** Spanish trawlers below 18 m (2 segments) and Italian trawlers between 12 and 18 m (1 segment) were generally profitable, except for during one or two years between 2014 and 2022.
- ➔ **Segments that were not sufficiently profitable:** Spanish trawlers above 18 m (2 segments), Italian trawlers above 18 m (2 segments) and French trawlers below 18 m (1 segment) were generally profitable but at levels that are not considered sufficient to remunerate sufficiently the capital invested in the vessels.

➔ Segments that were consistently unprofitable:

- Italian trawlers under 12 m (1 segment) have been unprofitable since 2019 and were just above the break-even point (i.e. where total revenue equals total costs) in 2022.
- Large French trawlers (over 24 m; 1 segment) have been consistently unprofitable for years, with negative levels of return on investment. This segment has remained active despite incurring losses for years. These trawlers benefited from a permanent cessation measure in late 2022: the effect of this measure will only be felt and recorded in subsequent years.

Table 3. Profitability of the trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean, based on the key indicators: Net Profit Margin, Return on Investment (ROI), Return on Fixed Tangible Assets (ROFTA), and crew remuneration.

Country	Trawler fleet segment	Net Profit Margin	ROI and ROFTA	Crew remuneration	Overall status
France 	18-24 m	Not sufficiently profitable	Profitable	Above national FTE average	Not sufficiently profitable
	24-40 m	Constantly unprofitable	Constantly unprofitable	Above national FTE average	Unprofitable
Italy 	6-12 m	Unprofitable for several years	Unprofitable for several years	Below national FTE average	Unprofitable
	12-18 m	Regularly profitable	Profitable	Below national FTE average	Profitable
	18-24 m	Unprofitable for several years	Profitable	Below national FTE average	Not sufficiently profitable
	24-40 m	Unprofitable for several years	Profitable	Below national FTE average	Not sufficiently profitable
Spain 	6-12 m	Regularly profitable	Profitable	Below national FTE average	Profitable
	12-18 m	Regularly profitable	Profitable	Below national FTE average	Profitable
	18-24 m	Not sufficiently profitable	Profitable	Below national FTE average	Not sufficiently profitable
	24-40 m	Not sufficiently profitable	Profitable	Below national FTE average	Not sufficiently profitable

Source: Data from Prellezo et al. (2024).⁵

It should be noted that a limited subset of segments has depended on subsidies to be profitable (although insufficiently so) rather than unprofitable, and only for particular years: France 18-24 m in 2014, Italy 18-24 m in 2014 and 2021, Italy 24-40 m in 2021, and Italy 6-12 m and Spain 24-40 m in 2022. Thanks to subsidies, six segments shifted from being insufficiently profitable to profitable: France 18-24 m in 2020, Italy 6-12 m in 2014, Italy 12-18 m in 2021, Spain 6-12 m in 2022, Spain 12-18 m in 2019, and Spain 18-24 m in 2017.

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3. Balance between fishing capacity and fishing opportunities

The existence of fleets which are not in balance with the resource they exploit has been an important driving force behind the historic overexploitation of resources in European waters.¹⁵ A fleet segment is considered unbalanced (or in a situation of imbalance) when it is too large for the available resources on which the vessels rely. When this unbalanced situation persists, Member States are required to implement measures to adjust the fishing capacity of their fleets to their fishing opportunities over time (Article 22 of the CFP²). A dedicated STECF working group evaluates

annually whether the capacity of EU fleet segments is considered to be balanced with the available fishing opportunities.¹⁶ The working group evaluates ten indicators to determine the status of each segment, following the key rule that no conclusion should be drawn from a single indicator: estimating that a fleet segment is out of balance relies on the convergence of several indicators. The indicators used are presented in Table 4 and are described in more details in the Methodological Annex (see Section 7.2.).

Table 4. List of balance indicators used by the STECF to assess balance between fleet capacity and fishing opportunities.

Biological indicators	Economic indicators
<p>The Stock at Risk (SAR) indicator identifies the number of biologically vulnerable stocks affected by the activities of a fleet segment.</p>	<p>The ratio between current revenue and break-even revenue (CR/BER ratio) measures the economic capability of the fleet segment to sustain fishing operations on a day-to-day basis: does income cover the costs of the crew, fuel, and vessel running expenses?</p>
<p>The Sustainable Harvest Indicator (SHI) measures the extent to which a fleet segment relies on stocks that are overfished.</p>	
Technical indicators	<p>The Return on Investment (ROI) and the Return on Fixed Tangible Assets (ROFTA) indicators compare the long-term profitability of the fishing fleet segment to other available investments.</p>
<p>The Economic Dependency Indicator (EDI) indicates how a fleet segment's fishing income is reliant on stocks exploited at rates inconsistent with MSY.</p>	<p>The Net Profit Margin (NP margin) measures the percentage of revenue retained as surplus after covering all explicit and implicit costs, including the opportunity costs of labour and capital.</p>
<p>The Vessel Utilisation Ratio (VUR) describes the intensity with which vessels in a fleet segment are utilised. The balance indicator tables include two sets of values for this indicator, using two baselines: VUR and VUR220^c.</p>	<p>The Net Value Added per Full-Time Equivalent Employment (NVA per FTE) indicator measures labour productivity by calculating the average net value generated by each full-time worker.</p>

Source: Casey *et al.* (2024).¹⁶

For the two biological indicators and three technical indicators, most of the trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean were assessed as being out of balance in 2022 (the most recent year for which data are available). As shown in Table 5, for 2022:

- ➔ The Stock at Risk (SAR) and the Sustainable Harvest Indicator (SHI) pointed towards a situation out of balance for all segments, except for French trawlers under 24 m and Italian trawlers under 12 m, even if there was a positive trend in the SAR indicator for the latter.

c. VUR is based on a theoretical maximum Days at Sea (DAS) submitted voluntarily by Member States, while VUR220 is based on a reference DAS of 220 days.

- The Economic Dependency Indicator (EDI) was too high for all segments for which it could be estimated, despite some improvement between 2018 and 2022 for most of the segments analysed. An EDI that is too high indicates an economic over-reliance on stocks that are depleted.
- The Vessel Utilisation Ratios (VUR) were too low for all French and Italian trawler segments, indicating that there may have been some latent capacity in these fleet segments in 2022. By contrast, these ratios were in balance for all the Spanish trawler segments. This means that the same level of production could have been achieved with fewer vessels deployed at full utilisation ratio. An underutilisation is often synonymous with lower profit levels

because of the existence of fixed costs. For most segments, there was no clear trend in these indicators over the previous five years. These segments were all regulated by the West Med MAP, which imposed more restrictions on fishing effort, and thus mechanically lowered the utilisation ratio.

The two biological and three technical indicators therefore pointed towards a generalised situation of unbalance: **there are too many vessels targeting too few fish.**

Table 5. Biological and technical balance indicators for the trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean in 2018 and 2022, along with 2018-2022 trends. SAR: Stock at Risk, SHI: Sustainable Harvest Indicator, EDI: Economic Dependency Indicator, VUR: Vessel Utilisation Ratio, VUR220: Vessel Utilisation Ratio based on 220 Days at Sea.

		Status 2018					Status 2022					Trends 2018-2022			
Country	Vessel Length	SAR	SHI	EDI	VUR	VUR220	SAR	SHI	EDI	VUR	VUR220	SHI	EDI	VUR	VUR220
France	18-24 m														
	24-40 m														
Italy	6-12 m														
	12-18 m														
	18-24 m														
	24-40 m														
Spain	6-12 m														
	12-18 m														
	18-24 m														
	24-40 m														

■ In balance

■ Out of balance

■ Borderline

■ No data

■ Improving

■ Deteriorating

■ No clear trend

■ No data

Source: Adapted from Casey et al. (2024).¹⁶

From an economic perspective, the situation was similarly problematic for most trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean, as depicted in Table 6. For all trawler segments except Spanish trawlers under 12 m, a majority of the economic capacity indicators have shown a declining five-year trend, with capacity indicators for several segments that indicate unbalanced situations:

- ⌚ In 2022, the ratio between current revenue and break-even revenue (CR/BER ratio) was out of balance for all segments over 24 m (for France, Italy, and Spain) and for Italian trawlers from 12 to 18 m. The five-year trend for this indicator was deteriorating for most segments, except for Spanish vessels under 12 m.
- ⌚ The net profit margin (NP margin) and the return on investment (ROI and ROFTA) were low or negative for most trawler segments, placing the segments out of balance in 2022. In 2018, French

trawlers over 24 m represented the only segment with these three indicators out of balance, with four other segments with a net profit margin considered borderline (France 18-24 m, Italy 6-12 m and 18-24 m, and Spain 24-40 m). The five-year trend of the indicators was deteriorating for all Italian trawler segments and all Spanish trawlers except for vessels under 12 m. When these three indicators are ranked borderline or out of balance, the remuneration of the capital invested by vessel owners when they acquired their vessels can be considered unattractive compared to other investments, placing the future of fleet renewal in serious jeopardy.

- ⌚ The net value added per FTE (NVA/FTE) was considered in balance in 2018 and in 2022 for all trawler segments. This indicator has, however, shown a deteriorating trend for all segments except Spanish trawlers under 12 m and French trawlers above 24 m.

Table 6. Economic balance indicators for the trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean in 2018 and 2022, and 2018-2022 trends. CR / BER: ratio between current revenue and break-even revenue, ROFTA: Return on Fixed Tangible Assets, ROI: Return on Investment, NP margin: Net Profit Margin, NVA / FTE: Net Value Added per Full-Time Equivalent Employment.

Source: Adapted from Casey et al. (2024).¹⁶

The combination of the five economic balance indicators and their five-year trends point towards a situation of **significant imbalance for all trawler segments present in the western Mediterranean**, apart from Spanish trawlers under 12 m length.

The biological, technical, and economic capacity indicators were combined by assessing the proportion of indicators that categorised each fleet segment as being in balance, borderline, and out of balance (see Table 7).

Table 7. Combination of the balance indicators for the trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean in 2018 and 2022, and 2018-2022 trends. For each segment, numbers shown summarise how many of the indicators presented in Tables 4 and 5 suggest that the segment is in balance, borderline, out of balance, or could be assessed due to insufficient data.

Country	Vessel length	Number of vessels (2022)	Status 2018				Status 2019				Trends 2018-2022			
			In balance	Borderline	Out of balance	No data	In balance	Borderline	Out of balance	No data	Improving	Deteriorating	No clear trend	No data
France 	18-24 m	29	5	1	1	3	5	1	2	2	1	3	3	2
	24-40 m	29	1		6	3	1		7	2	2	2	3	2
Italy 	6-12 m	665	5		4	1	5		5		1	4	4	
	12-18 m		5		5		1		9			6	3	
	18-24 m		6	1	3		2		8		2	6	1	
	24-40 m		7		1	2	1		9		2	6	1	
Spain 	6-12 m	24	4		1	5	5		3	2	5		2	2
	12-18 m	139	7		2	1	4	1	5		1	6	2	
	18-24 m	284	7		3		6	1	3		2	5	2	
	24-40 m	124	6	1	3		1		9		2	5	2	

Source: Data from Casey et al. (2024).¹⁶

The situation of the western Mediterranean trawler segments is rather grim: all segments had at least one indicator that pointed toward an unbalanced situation in 2018. Between 2018 and 2022, all segments had more indicators showing deteriorating trends than indicators presenting improving trends, except for Spanish trawlers under 12 m. This indicates that, overall, **the imbalance situation worsened for all these segments**. Except for the smallest Spanish trawlers (6-12 m), all trawler segments had more indicators that were out of balance in 2022 than in 2018. It should be noted that the current interpretation implemented in the STECF Balance indicators report¹⁶ is that **Member States are required to define a management plan to reduce their fleet capacity as soon as one or two indicators show an imbalance**.

4. Spillover analysis

Implementing additional restrictions on some fleet segments (as is the case with the trawling fleet in the western Mediterranean) is expected to affect not only the vessels subject to the restrictions, but also other vessels taking part in the same fishery. These effects have been widely modelled in the economic literature and have been documented in numerous fisheries.^{17,18} Once a group of fishing vessels is subject to further restrictions (e.g. lower fishing effort, more stringent quotas, or increased selectivity), the restricted vessels are likely to experience a short-term decline in their catch levels, while other vessels in the fishery may benefit from these management changes by increasing their share of catch.

To explore if such spillover impacts can be observed as a result of management measures under the West Med MAP, the latest Fisheries Dependent Information (FDI) data¹⁹ were analysed, as they cover a more extended time period than the AER data (see Section 7.3). The FDI data collection gathers

comprehensive information on the activity of EU fishing vessels, including fishing effort, landings, catches, fleet capacity, and biological data. Although the FDI data currently available do not allow the identification of country level information, their granularity is sufficient for analysing the catch and effort for each gear group.

Among the six species mentioned in the West Med MAP, European hake and red mullet were the two species of interest for this analysis, as they can be captured not only by trawlers, but also by vessels deploying passive gears. These passive gears are regrouped in three segments: nets (DFN), hooks (HOK), and polyvalent passive gears (PGP).^d

Both species have shown the same pattern in landed volumes and values in recent years (see Figure 6 and Figure 7): for all gear types combined, quantities landed in the western Mediterranean have generally declined, a trend that has continued since the launch of the West Med MAP. However, this post-2019 decline in catches has not yet resulted in rebounds in the stocks.⁴

In the case of those vessels that have been less affected or unaffected by the West Med MAP, the plan has not produced the side-effect of a significant increase in European hake and red mullet catch during the period of reference (i.e. until 2023). The vessels categorised as using passive gears (PGP) have also shown declines in their catches of European hake in 2022 and 2023.

European Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

Red Mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

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d. PGP regroups polyvalent vessels that deploy passive gears (hooks, nets, lines, pots), but cannot be assigned to a unique gear group.

Figure 6. Temporal trends in the quantities (left) and values (right) landed for European hake in the West Med MAP area, 2015-2023. DFN: drift and fixed nets, DTS: demersal trawl/seine, HOK: hooks, PGP: polyvalent passive gears.

Evolution of the quantities landed - Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

Evolution of the value landed - Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

DFN DTS HOK PGP Other

Source: Data from Zanzi et al. (2024).¹⁹

Figure 7. Temporal trends in the quantities (left) and values (right) landed for red mullet in the West Med Map area, 2015-2023. DFN: drift and fixed nets, DTS: demersal trawl/seine, HOK: hooks, PGP: polyvalent passive gears.

Evolution of the quantities landed - Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

Evolution of the value landed - Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

DFN DTS HOK PGP Other

Source: Data from Zanzi et al. (2024).¹⁹

5. Conclusions

The economic analysis of the trawler segments directly affected by the Western Mediterranean Multiannual Plan (West Med MAP) reveals a persistent and alarming lack of profitability across most trawler segments, both before and after its implementation. The majority of vessels – including all Italian trawler segments, French trawlers under 24 metres, and Spanish trawlers over 18 metres – have consistently exhibited low or negative profit margins, undermining their long-term viability. Among these, the situation is particularly critical for French trawlers over 24 metres, which face a chronic lack of profitability. While a buyback scheme has been introduced in France to address this issue, its implementation post-2022 means that any potential positive effects are not yet visible in the currently available data. Similarly, Italy is implementing a buyback scheme in 2025, which will only be visible in the data by 2028.

Profit levels remain critically low, rendering capital remuneration unattractive and placing the future of fleet renewal in serious jeopardy, a situation that persists despite various public subsidies that have been distributed to compensate for the West Med Map (at least 7.5 million euros), the COVID-19 pandemic (at least 2.6 million euros) and the energy crisis following the Ukraine war (at least 9.1 million euros). Given these persistently low profit levels, the sector possesses no inherent financial buffer or room for manoeuvre. Under these conditions, fleet renewal is financially unfeasible without substantial external support, whether public or private.

This crisis is fundamentally driven by a structural imbalance within the fleet, where an excess of vessels is competing for a limited resource base, leading to intense pressure on fish stocks. **The imbalance between fishing capacity and available fishing opportunities predates the West Med MAP and has deteriorated further since 2020.** Despite regulatory efforts to reduce fishing pressure and restore stock abundance, the fundamental issue persists: **the fleet remains oversized compared to the dwindling resources it depends on.** This structural

overcapacity not only jeopardises the economic survival of the trawler segments but also hinders the recovery of demersal stocks, perpetuating a cycle of overfishing and financial instability.

Despite the various restrictions implemented as part of the West Med MAP, there is a lack of apparent impact of the plan, with most fish populations still showing weak signs of recovery. Furthermore, this study found no evidence yet of a meaningful spillover effect resulting from the West Med MAP's restrictions. The anticipated redistribution of fishing opportunities to less impacted gear types, such as passive gears, has not yet materialised, as landings for species like European hake and red mullet continued to decline across all segments. This absence of spillover underscores the systemic nature of the challenge: reducing effort in one segment does not automatically translate into benefits for others, particularly when rebuilding fish populations can take years and when overall fleet capacity remains misaligned with the available resources.

Consequently, a strategic shift in management is urgently required, based on a more transformative approach. **Public intervention should be strategically targeted away from subsidising unprofitable vessels and instead towards promoting a gear transition.** This entails incentivising adaptations that reduce the prevalence of bottom trawling and encourage a shift towards more selective and sustainable methods, such as hooks and nets. Ultimately, **restoring balance will necessitate a reduction in overall fleet capacity,** achievable through mechanisms such as public buyback schemes and policies that encourage voluntary fleet consolidation.

6. Recommendations

Western Mediterranean fisheries require decisive policy intervention on multiple fronts. Short-term actions are necessary to enforce current regulations and accelerate stock recovery, while long-term strategies must address the structural issues of fleet imbalance and economic fragility. Below are outlined specific recommendations for achieving these objectives.

Short-term recommendations (immediate action)

1. Eliminate overcapacity to ensure lasting sustainability:

Western Mediterranean trawler segments have faced structural overcapacity since long before the adoption of the West Med MAP. The analysis in this report shows that seven trawler segments (France 12-24 m, France 24-40 m, Italy 6-12 m, Italy 18-24 m, Italy 24-40 m, Spain 18-24 m, Spain 24-40 m) continue to operate with insufficient or negative profitability, reflecting an imbalance between fishing capacity and available resources. Only three trawler segments are considered profitable over the period 2014-2020 (Italy 12-18 m, Spain 6-12 m, Spain 12-18 m). There is a need to reduce latent capacity by encouraging vessels that are unprofitable to leave the fishery. This has already been partially achieved through the implementation of permanent cessation measures, but some of these measures may have been implemented too late to allow any improvement to be reflected in the most recent available data. Targeted decommissioning of vessels, implemented through robust, fishery-specific capacity adjustment plans, should be prioritised. These measures must also include safeguards to prevent the transfer or relocation of redundant capacity to other regions, such as central and eastern EU Member States or North Africa, ensuring that any public funds support a genuine and fair transition toward a sustainable fleet structure.

2. Recover fish stocks to increase catches per unit effort:

Restoring fish populations will increase the productivity of the fishery (higher catches per day at sea) and improve the fleet's economic performance over time. While the latest data indicate early signs of recovery for most stocks, overall populations remain below sustainable levels, and continued management action is needed to secure full rebuilding. Available management measures under the West Med MAP to reduce fishing mortality – such as restrictions in fishing days, adoption of catch limits, temporary closures for severely overfished species, and improvements in selectivity – should be considered and enforced without loopholes to accelerate the rebuilding of stocks that remain below MSY levels.

3. Support fishers and communities through a just transition:

Achieving sustainable fisheries in the western Mediterranean requires a fair and inclusive transition. While decisive management measures are essential to ensure the long-term viability of the sector, they can impose short-term hardship on fishers and coastal communities. Targeted, time-bound support, including financial compensation or income aid, as well as retraining and job diversification programmes, should therefore be provided for those facing immediate losses due to fishing mortality reductions and fleet capacity adjustments. Such support will ease the socioeconomic impact of conservation measures, maintain social cohesion, and help secure industry buy-in for necessary changes. Importantly, public funds should support a just transition: not to perpetuate unsustainable practices, but to help people adapt to evolving realities in the fisheries sector.

Long-term recommendations (structural and strategic measures)

4. Reorient public financial support for long-term sustainability:

Harmful subsidies that contribute to overcapacity and overfishing or delay essential reforms must be phased out. Instead, public financial support, including EU structural funds like the EMFAF and Member State aid, should be channelled into measures that deliver lasting socio-economic and environmental benefits. This means financing vessel scrapping programmes, gear changes, and business diversification initiatives. Additionally, support should be available for fishers who choose to seek re-skilling assistance. Policymakers should avoid supporting unprofitable and unsustainable practices and instead invest in the future: a smaller, more resilient and selective fleet targeting recovered fish stocks. This strategic use of public funds will strengthen both the health of marine environment and the long-term viability of fishing communities.

5. Assess and promote a gear transition to more sustainable fishing methods:

The transition toward more sustainable fishing practices has the potential to improve the long-term sustainability of Mediterranean fisheries and reduce ecosystem pressures. However, such a shift must be guided by sound biological and economic evidence. Before promoting gear transitions, the economic viability, market potential, and ecological footprint of alternative gears—such as longlines and gillnets—should be assessed to determine whether they can realistically absorb part of the existing trawling capacity without creating new sustainability or profitability challenges. Public support should focus on enabling a measured and evidence-based transition. When proven viable, incentives for gear modification and adoption of more selective techniques can improve catch quality, reduce discards and bycatch, and increase product value. Crucially, such initiatives must complement, not replace, the broader objectives of eliminating overcapacity and rebuilding fish stocks.

6. Standardise reporting of operating subsidies:

The current reporting system lacks transparency. Subsidies data are often fragmented, inconsistent, not centralised and sometimes not reported and/or not publicly available. It is essential to obtain full transparency on public support via the publication of standardised data across all Member States, in order to allow the best use of public funds. This will promote the implementation of profitable and sustainable practices, thus ultimately supporting adaptation and long-term resilience in the sector.

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7. Integrate more economic thinking in the West Med MAP:

The West Med MAP represents a significant step forward in restoring key demersal species and promoting sustainable fisheries in the western Mediterranean, offering a valuable opportunity to also address the economic vitality of the sector. Strengthening profit levels would complement the MAP's environmental goals, ensuring that both fish populations and livelihoods thrive in the long term. By integrating economic resilience into the MAP's implementation, decision-makers can secure lasting benefits for the sector. Achieving the MAP's objectives will create a foundation for sustainable fisheries, but maintaining this balance will require continued commitment to preventing overcapacity and overfishing. With proactive management, the West Med MAP can pave the way for a more sustainable, prosperous, and resilient fishing industry.

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7. Methodological annex

Three reports published annually by the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) constitute the basis of the information used to prepare this report:

- ➔ The Annual Economic Report (AER)⁵
- ➔ The Balance Indicators report¹⁶
- ➔ The Fisheries Dependent Information (FDI) report¹⁹

The data from these reports have been complemented with details on subsidies paid by each Member State.^{7,8,9}

» 7.1 Annual Economic Report (AER)

The STECF Annual Economic Report (AER)⁵ is the basis of the economic information used to prepare this report. It comprises economic data, collected systematically and disaggregated at the segment level, including details on catch quantities and values by species and by geographical zones.

For the Mediterranean, the catch data are available at the geographical subarea (GSA)³ level. However, economic data (income and expenditures) are aggregated at the level of the Mediterranean and Black Sea.

There are some limitations in the data for this particular study:

- ➔ Fleet segments are defined based on their principal area of operation:
 - Some Spanish segments present in the Mediterranean also operate on the Atlantic side (West of Gibraltar), although most of their activities are carried out in the western Mediterranean.
 - The Italian segments aggregate the entire Italian coast, including the Ionian and

» 7.2 Balance indicators

The results presented in the latest Balance Indicators report¹⁶ allow for the evaluation of whether the capacity of trawler segments operating in the western Mediterranean can be considered out of balance with fishing opportunities. As with the AER data, the capacity indicators show a two-year lag. The data available for the preparation of this report only cover years until 2022, as the most recent Balance Indicators report was published during the autumn of 2024. This is notable because some of these indicators rely on the data collected for

Adriatic Seas. Data are adjusted using the latest publication produced by NISEA.²⁰

- ➔ Because of the process involved in collecting the data, the AER data lag by two years. The data available for the preparation of this report only cover years up to 2022, as the most recent AER report⁵ was published in autumn 2024. The 2023 data will only become public later in 2025.

The AER dataset details several key economic indicators at the segment level, including income information, key costs (notably crew remuneration and energy costs), subsidies (operating subsidies and (dis)investment subsidies), depreciation, and financial costs. These economic data are complemented by:

- ➔ Technical information such as average age, engine power (in kW), gross tonnage;
- ➔ Activity information such as days at sea;
- ➔ Detailed landing statistics, in quantities and values.

the AER report. The 2023 data will only become public later in 2025.

The Balance Indicators report¹⁶ builds on ten indicators that should be considered in combination to assess whether the segment analysed is considered out of balance: two biological indicators, three technical indicators, and five economic indicators that are estimated annually by the working group responsible.

Biological indicators

- The **Stock at Risk indicator (SAR)** identifies how many stocks that are biologically vulnerable are being affected by the activities of a fleet segment. The SAR is estimated for each segment, providing an aggregate score that covers all targeted stocks. Suppose a fleet segment takes more than 10% of its catches from a stock which is at risk, or the fleet segment takes 10% or more of the European fleets' total catches from a stock at risk. In that case, the Balance Indicator Guidelines¹⁵ suggest that this could be treated as an indication of imbalance.
- The **Sustainable Harvest Indicator (SHI)** measures the extent to which a fleet segment relies on stocks that are overfished. As with the SAR, the SHI is an aggregate indicator. Values of the indicator above 1 indicate that a fleet segment is, on average, relying on fishing opportunities set at levels too high to be consistent with MSY. A value of the indicator above 1 could be an indication of an imbalance if it has occurred for three consecutive years.

Technical indicators

- The **Economic Dependency Indicator (EDI)** indicates how a fleet segment's fishing income is reliant on stocks exploited at rates inconsistent with MSY (i.e. for which the ratio of F/F_{MSY} is greater than 1). The EDI represents the cumulative proportion of the revenue from such stocks to that fleet segment. If the EDI score reaches 20%, this may be an indication of imbalance. Segments are considered borderline if EDI scores are close to 20% (between 17.5% and 20%).
- The **Vessel Utilisation Ratio (VUR)** describes the intensity with which vessels in a fleet segment are utilised. This indicator concerns the average activity levels of vessels that fished at least once during the year, considering the seasonality of the fishery and other restrictions. The balance indicator tables include two sets of values for this indicator: **VUR** per fleet segment is based on a theoretical maximum Days at Sea (DAS) submitted voluntarily by some Member States, and **VUR220** per fleet segment is based on a reference DAS of 220 days. If the average activity level of vessels in a fleet segment is recurrently less than 70% of the potential workable activity of comparable vessels, this could indicate technical inefficiency, which may reveal the existence of an imbalance.

Economic indicators

- ③ The **ratio between current revenue and break-even revenue (CR/BER ratio)** measures the economic capability of the fleet segment to sustain fishing operations on a day-to-day basis: does income cover the costs of the crew, fuel, and vessel running expenses? The threshold ratio value that is considered to suggest potential imbalance is $CR / BER = 1$. If the estimated ratio value is below 1, there may be an imbalance.
- ③ The **Return on Investment (ROI)** and the **Return on Fixed Tangible Assets (ROFTA)** indicators compare the long-term profitability of the fishing fleet segment to other available investments. The threshold used to suggest potential imbalance for a specific fleet segment is the low-risk long-term investment rate for the Member State where the fleet segment is registered.²¹ If the ROI is lower than the threshold, then this suggests that the fleet segment may be overcapitalised (i.e. a fleet segment has invested more capital - e.g. vessels, gear, equipment - than it can profitably sustain, resulting in low returns compared to alternative low-risk investments).
- ③ The **Net Profit Margin (NP margin)** measures the percentage of revenue retained as surplus after covering all explicit and implicit costs, including the opportunity costs of labour and capital. It reflects the economic profit and resource rent generated by fisheries, indicating their operating efficiency and capacity to generate surplus compared to alternative uses of labour and capital in the economy. A negative NP margin indicates an imbalance, while a positive NP margin suggests balance. Values below 10% are considered insufficiently profitable, as defined in the Balance Indicators reports.
- ③ The **Net Value Added per Full-Time Equivalent Employment (NVA per FTE)** indicator measures labour productivity by calculating the average net value generated by each full-time worker. A negative NVA per FTE ratio signifies imbalance, while a positive value indicates balance. However, an NVA per FTE ratio below €1500 suggests insufficient labour productivity, implying that the sector is not generating enough value added per worker.

» 7.3 Fisheries Dependent Information (FDI)

The Fisheries Dependent Information (FDI) report¹⁹ comprises detailed fisheries effort, catch, and landings data at a disaggregated level, allowing the analysis of the evolution of the activity at the GSA level.

Due to the process involved in collecting the data, the FDI data only lags by one year. The data used for the preparation of this report cover years until 2023, as the dataset was published in the autumn of 2024.

» 7.4 Data on subsidies

Two categories of subsidies are defined in the STECF guidelines:²²

1. **Operating subsidies** are direct payments that central and local governments or the institutions of the European Union make to resident producers (ESA D.3). They refer to direct payments/transfers related to the vessel activity, except for fuel tax refunds, subsidies for permanent cessation of fishing activities, and investment subsidies (fleet modernisation).
2. **Subsidies on investments** are direct payments that central and local governments or the institutions of the European Union make to resident producers to finance all or part of the costs of acquiring assets related to the vessel.

The guidelines indicate that subsidies for the permanent cessation of fishing activities of vessels that have become inactive during the year are attributed to inactive ships. Several Mediterranean segments benefited from this type of support, as noted in the latest Balance Indicator report, notably the French trawlers in 2022-2023 and more recently some Italian trawlers.¹⁶

Data on specific operating subsidies have been obtained for each Member State (France, Italy, and Spain). The initial datasets (one per Member State) were collected in preparation for the STECF Expert Working Group EWG 24-12 "Fishing effort regime for demersal fisheries in West Med", held in October 2024.¹⁰ These datasets were rechecked during this project to assess whether national and regional administrations later released additional information to better describe the subsidies paid to the fishing vessels operating in the western Mediterranean.

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